

BRITAIN IN SPACE

FOREWORD

Britain is by no means a newcomer to Space.

This brochure is intended to give a brief account of Britain's space activities, and to illustrate the scientific and technological capability that exists in the UK.

The British National Space Centre's role is outlined in the first section of the brochure. The other sections combine two functions: they illustrate the sorts of activity which fall within the Centre's terms of reference, and they bring the reader up to date with the UK's experience, capability and current work in these sectors.

The BNSC has recently completed a first version of a National Space Plan which makes recommendations on Britain's space programme for the next decade. The Plan is at present under examination by Government, and a decision on the programmes and funding is expected before the end of 1986.

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Roy Gibson". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

Roy Gibson
Director-General
British National Space Centre

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BNSC: THE UK'S FOCUS FOR SPACE ACTIVITIES

British scientists and engineers have played an important part in space development right from the start of space exploration some 30 years ago.

Britain was a main pioneer of research in space astronomy, for example, and subsequently developed its own launch vehicle, accumulating in the process an enviable understanding of satellite technology and instrumentation. It now has an impressive capability in most aspects of space.

But space is one of the most expensive of the high technologies to exploit, and few countries can afford to stay at the forefront from their own resources. Most depend on international co-operation. That is why the UK became an enthusiastic founder member of the European Space Agency in 1975.

Since then the commercial and scientific opportunities presented by space have become even more attractive, and the UK Government's formation of the British National Space Centre (BNSC) in November 1985 was both a recognition of this fact and a commitment to the future.

The aim was to provide a single focus for Britain's space effort in science and technology, and to establish a single channel for Government sponsorship of the industry. The BNSC has started to bring together the various space R&D activities and responsibilities previously spread among a number of organisations (Government departments, the Universities, the Research Councils, and Industry), and is therefore already laying the foundations for a co-ordinated policy on space, a common technology base, and a strategy for consolidating and expanding British industrial competitiveness in this field.

The Centre operates with a mix of staff drawn from the main organisations concerned with space: The Department of Trade and Industry The Ministry of Defence The Science and Engineering Research Council The Natural Environment Research Council.

As a result of this amalgamation, the BNSC now co-ordinates most of the Government's space activities. The Director-General reports to the Minister of State for Information Technology in the Department of Trade and Industry.

As the UK's representative to the European Space Agency (ESA), the BNSC helps define the Agency's programmes – technological, scientific, earth observation, meteorological, telecommunications, launcher, space stations, micro-gravity, and others. It administers the Department of Trade and Industry's grants for R&D to the space industries, and it also advises the Department of Trade and Industry on the space activities of international space organisations (eg, Intelsat, Inmarsat, Eutelsat). It is similarly responsible for the SERC grants for space science to the Universities.

The BNSC's aim therefore is to ensure the best possible use of UK technology and resources, whether for industry, science or defence, by running some civil and defence space interests together. Among other things, this is intended to smooth and shorten the route by which the results of publicly funded research are transferred to the commercial sector.

The European Space Agency's programmes remain the keystone of British space activities, and Britain will continue to play a major role in the Agency's activities.

COMMUNICATIONS SATELLITES

Britain's involvement with satellite communications has been long, traditional and fruitful. Within ESA application programmes, the UK concentrated on this field as the quickest route to a profitable space industry, and today about half of British expenditure through the European Space Agency goes to the telecommunications programme. As a result British industry has now attained a world reputation in the design, manufacture and supply of communications satellites.

Its expertise was gained initially through involvement in the ESA communications satellites (OTS, ECS and MARECS). Subsequently UK companies (Marconi and British Aerospace) have been involved in successive generations of satellites for the three main user organisations: INTELSAT (international global communications in the fixed service network), EUTELSAT (European regional multi-service communications), and INMARSAT (maritime communications).

The UK has participated in the development and construction of all the US-produced INTELSAT satellites from II to VI.

The European Space Agency's Orbital Test Satellite (OTS) launched in 1978 was the first European communications satellite. The ECS followed, with EUTELSAT as the customer, and MARECS (a maritime derivative, for which Marconi developed the payload) was subsequently produced for INMARSAT. All the ECS and MARECS satellites were constructed by British Aerospace. The ECS design has also been used as the basis of the British Ministry of Defence's SKYNET IV.

In all, five ECS and three MARECS satellites have been ordered. All three of the latter have been delivered. ECS-1 and ECS-2 (launched in 1983 and 1984) now make up the EUTELSAT space segment which provides telephony, data and television distribution services throughout Western Europe.

Right. OLYMPUS is to be launched in 1988 as a technology demonstrator for a family of multi-purpose communications satellites which will be among the largest and most powerful in the world. The biggest could have in-orbit weights up to 3700 kg and generate 7.7 kW from solar arrays of 60 m span.

Left. British Aerospace is prime contractor for Olympus 1.

The ECS-based SKYNET IV military communications satellite designed for the UK's armed forces. It has UHF and SHF capabilities, and communication links can be established via man-pack ground equipment. Three satellites have been ordered.

INMARSAT: Ship to Shore Telecommunications. INMARSAT has six satellites in geo-stationary orbit over the Atlantic, Indian and Pacific Oceans, providing global telecommunications cover for ships and offshore platforms. Two European MARECS satellites, part of this system, operate over the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans. The Operational Control Centre in London monitors the traffic flow – telephone, telex, data and facsimile, as well as emergency, distress and safety communications services.

Second-generation satellites are now being developed for both EUTELSAT and INMARSAT.

British Aerospace is leading an international team on INMARSAT II, which is expected to go into service during the 1990's. INMARSAT II is based on British Aerospace's and the French company MATRA's EUROSTAR – a larger development of the ECS spacecraft which will provide many more times the capacity of today's system, permit the use of smaller ship-to-earth stations and, in due course, include facilities for communications with aircraft.

Marconi is a member of the European consortium of companies producing EUTELSAT II.

OLYMPUS, another British Aerospace-led project, is the latest ESA communications satellite, scheduled for launch in 1988. What will emerge from the OLYMPUS project is a large, experimental, multi-purpose, high-power communications satellite designed to handle the following traffic: high-density trunk telephony, data and television traffic; specialised business services (the payload for which is being developed by Marconi Space Systems); communications with mobile vehicles; and high-power broadcasting of radio and television services for direct reception by domestic receivers.

INMARSAT II, a second-generation maritime communications satellite being built for INMARSAT. Facilities: 250 voice channels for ship-to-shore communications, and 125 for shore-to-ship links.

EARTH OBSERVATION

Earth observation by satellite covers two types of application, in both of which Britain is playing a notable role:

- the observation and study of atmospheric phenomena – eg, meteorology and atmospheric physics;
- the surveying of the earth's surface and natural resources – ie, remote sensing.

Meteorology

The first formal European meteorological satellite studies bore fruit in 1977 when METEOSAT was put into geo-stationary orbit. Long before that, however, British scientists were developing instruments (eg, the infrared radiometers developed at Oxford University for measuring atmospheric temperature profiles) for experiments put into space on US satellites.

Today two ESA METEOSATS (F1 and F2) operate as a single element in the space segment of the World Weather Watch, transmitting information to main World Weather Watch centres across the globe, including that co-located with the British Meteorological Office at Bracknell.

Marconi Space Systems, a major sub-contractor in the METEOSAT development programme, was responsible for the attitude-measurement system, the attitude-and orbit-control system, the imaging electronics and the communications packages of both the pre-operational satellites and the subsequent four operational craft.

A sister company, Marconi Defence Systems, is currently developing a five-channel Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit (AMSU-B) for the British Meteorological Office, ready for launch on an Advanced TIROS-N satellite in 1990. Designed to be particularly sensitive to ice clouds, and capable of sensing water-vapour profiles and precipitation over land and sea, it will be Europe's first space-borne sounder operating at a frequency of 200 GHz.

The development of meteorological satellites is paralleled by work on advanced sensors for atmospheric physics research. For example, Oxford University, with Rutherford Appleton Laboratory and British Aerospace, are developing the Improved Stratospheric and Mesospheric Sounder for the US Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite (UARS).

An Atlantic depression. A frontal system approaching North-West Scotland observed by the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer carried on the TIROS-N polar-orbiting satellite. Two of these satellites orbit in tandem, providing an image every 6 hours from a height of 850 km.

Below. A full view of the Earth from Meteosat in geo-stationary orbit 35,900 km above the equator. Images showing cloud patterns and developing storms are received every 30 minutes, day and night, enabling a close watch to be kept on continental weather systems, their rate and direction of movement, and the intensity of the weather associated with them.

Remote sensing

Observation of the Earth from space is widening our knowledge of our planet, and providing opportunities for scientific and commercial exploitation of the information collected (eg, for mineral exploration and mapping).

The major part of Britain's support for remote-sensing research and development is allocated to the European Space Agency's Earth Observation Programme, which includes the ERS-1 (the first ESA remote sensing satellite) and the EARTHNET data system.

Scheduled for launch in 1990, ERS-1 will provide a remote-sensing facility equipped to observe and monitor the ocean, coastal zones, land and polar regions under all weather conditions. For this the satellite will carry a comprehensive set of instruments, mainly microwave, and including an active Ku-band radar altimeter, a C-band Active Microwave Instrument (AMI), and a 3-channel IR radiometer.

Britain has been involved in every aspect of the ERS-1 programme since the late 1970's, with Government departments helping to define programme requirements, science groups in universities supporting various research activities, and industry carrying out design studies and supplying equipment.

As a major sub-contractor for the design and manufacture of the AMI, the instrument at the heart of the ERS-1 payload, Marconi Space Systems have an important part to play.

The AMI is designed to operate in three modes:

- In the imaging mode it will function as a synthetic-aperture radar, providing high-resolution images with a maximum resolution of 30 m.
- In the wind mode, over oceans, it will act as a scatterometer, measuring changes in radar reflectivity in a 500-km swath, from which surface wind speed and direction can be derived.

- In the wave mode the AMI will again operate as a synthetic-aperture radar, taking samples from which, in conjunction with other instruments, wave height and direction can be deduced.

The Along Track Scanning Radiometer, a combined infra-red and microwave radiometer, capable of measuring the surface temperature of the sea to an accuracy of ± 0.3 Kelvin (data which will be used for computing the ocean-atmosphere heat fluxes which drive the global climate system) is also to fly in ERS-1. The ATSR is being built by groups in Oxford University, the Mullard Space Science Laboratory of UCL, the Meteorological Office, and RAL, together with collaborators in France and Australia.

The BNSC's support for the Columbus programme, particularly the polar platforms (see page 18), reflects its support for remote sensing, for it sees these as a new generation of remote sensing vehicles which will increase the scope of the information gathered. The BNSC is also doing all it can to ensure that potential users are made aware of the value of remote-sensing data, and of the wide range of applications in which the images can be used.

Expert guidance on image processing and interpretation is available, and several British-developed software packages for processing the imagery into a form suitable for the applications scientists are on the market. The Royal Aircraft Establishment, for example, has developed a user-friendly interactive image-analysis system called GEMS, and, in co-operation with British companies working in the field, has designed and produced a SAR data processor – one of the few such systems in the world.

R&D on new applications of earth-observation data is also carried out by a number of key university groups and at the research institutes of the Natural Environment Research Council and the Science and Engineering Research Council. The data is fast becoming accepted as a basic tool by British companies; especially those working for overseas clients on land-resources development, exploration, geology and civil engineering.

One of the elements of the ESA's Earth Observation Programme is EARTHNET – an Agency organisation responsible for the collection and dissemination of remote-sensing data in Europe through a network of 'national points of contact'. The point of contact for the UK is the National Remote Sensing Centre.

The National Remote Sensing Centre was established at Farnborough in 1980 to increase national interest in remote sensing, and its primary function therefore is to provide potential users with images and image-processing facilities. The Centre is also very active in developing applications for remote-sensing data in such sectors as agriculture, forestry, bathymetry and geological surveying.

The remote-sensing data is supplied in various forms, including photographic reproductions of radar images, false-colour LANDSAT multi-spectral scanner images, and image overlays, masked images and composite illustrations prepared from analyses and other information.

As part of its awareness campaign, the Centre also sponsors a mobile 'Earth from Space' demonstration unit equipped to demonstrate the full potential of remote sensing to invited audiences from business and the education sector.

ERS-1, ESA's first remote-sensing satellite, is due to be launched in 1990. The Along Track Scanning Radiometer, a combined infra-red and microwave radiometer on which various groups in British universities are now working, will fly on it. Marconi Space Systems are major sub-contractors in the design and manufacture of another of its crucial sensing instruments – the AMI.

Vegetation monitoring. This false-colour image of the North East of England shows the North York Moors. The image, taken in May, depicts the extent of bracken growth (blue and grey tones) in relation to the surrounding farmland (red).

Spreading the remote-sensing message in the UK. The National Remote Sensing Centre's mobile demonstration unit tours the country giving seminars to invited audiences.

British scientists were among the first in the world to recognise and exploit the advantages of space. Many gained international reputations in the new astronomy, the studies of the sun and planets and the Earth's atmosphere, and put Britain at the forefront of space research. Since the 1960s the strong research teams in the universities and institutes have also won Britain a prominent place in the science programmes of ESA, NASA and other agencies: indeed, in ESA's

case, British experiments were carried on all but one of the fourteen science missions.

The most recent, and highly successful, mission was the GIOTTO space probe's encounter with Halley's Comet earlier this year. GIOTTO, the first European deep-space probe, was built by an international team led by British Aerospace. It included two UK experiments; the dust-impact detector system (Kept University) and the Johnstone plasma analyser

(Mullard Space Science Laboratory, UCL). The university teams are now analysing the vast amount of data collected.

British universities are also participating in ROSAT – a co-operative astrophysics programme, combining resources from the UK, Germany and the USA, which aims to place two telescopes in orbit to conduct the first X-ray imaging survey of the complete sky in a wavelength range from 6 Å to 300 Å

GIOTTO: the encounter.

Above: ESA's GIOTTO was launched by Ariane in July 1985, initially into a geo-synchronous transfer orbit. Thereafter it was boosted into a heliocentric trajectory to intercept Halley's Comet. The encounter occurred on 13 March 1986, and, throughout, experimental data was relayed back to Earth in real time. At the point of encounter GIOTTO was about 150 million km from Earth and 133 million km from the sun.

Right: The innermost coma, with dust jets and nucleus, can be seen on this image, taken by an on-board camera when GIOTTO was 25,650 km from the comet. The sun is on the right, 26 degrees below the horizontal and 16 degrees behind the image plane.

The two co-aligned telescopes, known as the X-ray Telescope (XRT) and Wide Field Camera (WFC), will first scan the sky in a systematic way with a spatial resolution of 2 arc-minutes at a rate of 4° per minute for 6 months. Subsequently, in a second phase of the mission, the instruments will operate as a space observatory, with finer resolution and longer observing time, focusing on specific objects, or regions of sky, for at least a further year. The spacecraft and the XRT are the responsibility of BMFT, Germany, and the WFC is being developed by a UK consortium of astrophysics research groups from Leicester University, Mullard Space Science Laboratory (MSSL), Birmingham University, Imperial College and Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL).

Over the last year RAL has been co-ordinating preparation for the operational phase of the mission with the WFC consortium. A single ground station in Germany will receive all data from ROSAT during 5-6 passes per day. Essential scientific data will be routed to WFC staff at a ROSAT Science Data Centre at the Max Planck Institut who will supervise the transmission of commands to the WFC and master data records to the UK. In the UK, data processing and analysis will be centralised at RAL for initial reduction and at Leicester University for final production of the results of the sky survey. All WFC consortium groups will participate in the survey analysis, and some of the pointed phase observations (which will be shared in an equitable way between the three collaborating nations) will

also be extended to guest observers.

AMPTE is another co-operative venture. The fourth state of matter, the plasma state, is common throughout the Universe, but since it is sustained only under conditions of very high temperature and/or very low density, it is not easy to examine on earth. The opportunity exists to examine a complete plasma system in situ where the Earth's atmosphere is ionised and forms a plasma round our planet, and the examination can be carried out either from the ground (using high power radars) or by space probe.

As part of the USA/Germany/UK Active Magnetospheric Particle Tracer Explorer mission (AMPTE), a UK sub-satellite (UKS) constructed by RAL and MSSL was launched in 1985. Experiments on UKS were provided

Below. CHASE – the Coronal Helium Abundance Experiment – was one of two UK experiments deployed aboard Challenger on the Spacelab 2 mission launched in July 1985. CHASE, built by groups at the Mullard Space Science Laboratory and the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, carried out spectroscopic studies of the solar corona in the extreme ultra violet.

Right. Some results showing the distribution of various elements in the hot gas of the sun's atmosphere.

UK involvement in Scientific Satellites 1975-1992				
SATELLITE	AGENCY	YEAR	PURPOSE	UK GROUPS INVOLVED
Ariel V	UK/US	1974	X-ray sky survey	UCL, Leicester, IC
GEOS-1	ESA	1977	Magnetospheric measurements	UCL (MSSL)
ISEE A,B	ESA/NASA	1977	Magnetospheric measurements	IC
IUE	UK/ESA/NASA	1978	UV spectroscopy	UCL, RAL
Pioneer Venus	NASA	1978	Atmosphere of Venus	Oxford
GEOS-2	ESA	1978	Waves and particles	UCL (MSSL), Sheffield
ISEE-C	ESA/NASA	1978	Magnetospheric measurements	IC
Ariel VI	UK	1979	X-ray and cosmic ray	Bristol, Leicester, UCL, Birmingham
SMM	NASA	1980	Solar maximum (X-ray)	Birmingham, Leicester, UCL (MSSL), RAL
EXOSAT	ESA	1983	X-ray observatory	UCL (MSSL), Leicester
Spacelab 1	NASA/ESA	1983	X-ray spectroscopy	UCL (MSSL)
AMPTE	US/UK/FRG	1984	Magnetospheric particles and structure	UCL (MSSL), RAL, IC
IRAS	US/UK/NL	1984	Infra-red sky survey	Sheffield, Sussex, BAS
Spacelab 2	NASA	1985	Coronal helium abundance	RAL, QMC
GIOTTO	ESA	1985	Hard X-ray imaging	UCL (MSSL), RAL
Viking	Sweden	1986	Halley comet encounter	Birmingham
Astro-C	Japan	1987	Earth radiation environment	Kent, UCL (MSSL), RAL, Sussex, RAL
Galileo	NASA	1988	X-ray source variability	Leicester, RAL
Hipparcos	ESA	1988	Jupiter orbiter and probe	Oxford
ROSAT	US/UK/FRG	1988	Star motion measurements	RAL, RGO, UCL (MSSL), Leicester, IC, Birmingham, UCL (MSSL), RAL
CRRESS	USAF	1988/89	X-ray and EUV observatory	UCL (MSSL), Sussex, RAL, IC
ULYSSES	ESA	1988/89	Earth radiation environment	UCL (MSSL), RAL
ISO	ESA	1992	Out of ecliptic solar polar regions	QMC, ROE, UCL, UCL (MSSL), IC, RAL
			Infra red observatory spectroscopy	

by the Universities of Sussex and Sheffield, Imperial College of Science and Technology, MSSL and RAL, with support from the University of Surrey. Ground measurements were made at the European incoherent scatter radar facility at Tromsø, Norway – the most northerly latitude ever achieved.

IRAS, the Infra-Red Astronomical Satellite, was launched in January 1983, and carried out its mission to survey the sky at infra-red wavelengths until November that year, when the supply of liquid-helium coolant became exhausted, and, as a result, the main instrument, a cryogenically-cooled telescope, ceased operation.

While it was operating IRAS viewed the whole sky twice and completed 70% of a third survey.

In addition to this survey, IRAS spent about 40% of its time mapping small regions of the sky in more detail and at higher sensitivity. The observations covered the interests of extra-galactic and galactic astronomy and solar system objects. About 10,000 additional observations were carried out. A year later, the images derived from these observations were released to the astronomical community, and the IRAS Post Mission Analysis Facility (IPMAF) was set up in 1984 at RAL to make the data available to UK astronomers. IPMAF makes use of the university STARLINK system of computers distributed around the UK at a number of centres of astronomical research.

IPMAF can combine the multiple raw survey observations to enable observation of objects three times fainter than previously possible, and allows the data to be used in detailed studies in a number of important areas such as star formation.

Finally, a rather more unusual project in this summary of some of the highlights of the space programmes. Taking advantage of NASA's offer to launch such satellites from the Space Shuttle, Surrey University constructed two low-cost satellites (UOSAT 1 and 2) from their own resources. Launched in 1981 and 1984, respectively, they have enabled amateur scientists to gain experience in space techniques, and have captured the imagination of young scientists in schools, colleges and universities.

Two of the seven experiments on the Solar Maximum Mission (SMM) were designed and built by UK groups in collaboration with overseas institutes. SMM, which was launched in 1980, operated successfully for 9 months before losing fine pointing control. In 1984 SMM was captured by the Space Shuttle and successfully repaired. The picture shows an astronaut approaching SMM during the rescue.

The UK AMPTE spacecraft. Built by Mullard Space Science Laboratory and Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, the spacecraft was launched in 1984, together with two companion spacecraft built by Germany and the US. The AMPTE mission studied the interaction of the solar wind with the Earth's magnetosphere, and created the first artificial comet.

The Ariel V satellite. Constructed by Marconi Space and Defence Systems, and launched in 1975 by NASA, it carried out a highly successful all-sky survey of X-ray sources. Groups from Imperial College, Leicester University, and University College London built instruments for the satellite, and its operation was controlled from the UK's Appleton Laboratory control centre.

HOTOL is a British concept, and the first to envisage a launch vehicle, recoverable or otherwise, which is not solely rocket-based. It pushes space technology into the next generation of launchers: horizontal take-off and landing, fully recoverable, single-stage-to-orbit, and low-cost. With a hybrid engine arrangement combining air-breathing and rocket propulsion, it is designed to meet all European, and most commercial, requirements well into the 21st Century.

HOTOL will take-off and land from Concorde class runways, just like conventional aircraft. And, unlike existing launch vehicles, which rely for first-stage propulsion on the combustion of hydrogen and oxygen from internal tanks, HOTOL will use its new form of air-breathing propulsion during the first part of its flight. It will incorporate a liquid-oxygen fuel tank, but only for flight outside the atmosphere, where air breathing is not possible. As a result the fuel carried (and hence the weight of the craft) will be much less than those typifying a conventional rocket launcher.

achieved at a height of 90 km, and the main propulsion system will then be cut, allowing the craft to coast on up and stabilise in orbit at an operational height of about 300 km.

Once in orbit, the on-board orbital manoeuvring system will make changes to the position and attitude, ready for the release of the payload. Satellites intended for geo-stationary orbit will be placed in low earth orbit, and then boosted into transfer orbit by an integral, or accompanying, perigee motor.

HOTOL will initially be unmanned, and will be used to deliver payloads into orbit. The design aim is for a payload capacity of seven tonnes or more in low-earth orbit. If this is achieved, launch costs into low earth orbit should be cut by a factor of five compared with those currently associated with the US Space Shuttle or Ariane.

BNSC is now jointly supporting full-scale proof-of-concept studies by British Aerospace and Rolls-Royce. The studies, which will last two years, are essentially to prove the engine and other technologies involved, prior to decisions on whether to move into a traditional development programme through the ESA.

To avoid the encumbrance of a heavy undercarriage capable of withstanding the all-up-weight on take-off, HOTOL will be launched from a simple ground trolley, and will need only a light-weight undercarriage to land. At a take-off speed of some 340 mph (550 kph) it will leave the trolley, and, climbing at an angle of about 24 degrees, reach a height of 40,000 ft (12,000 m), clear of all commercial airlines, some 4.5 to 5 minutes later. In less than 10 minutes, it will be some 26 km above the earth and travelling at a speed approaching Mach 4. By this time, air breathing will no longer be practicable, and the vehicle will be operating in the rocket-propulsion mode. Orbital velocity will be

SPACE LAUNCH SYSTEMS

Satellite launch systems have always been rocket-based. Nowadays, with the advent of NASA's Space Shuttle, they have diverged into two forms: expendable and recoverable.

Britain had early experience in the design and development of expendable launching systems, starting with the Skylark series of sounding rockets for space research in the 1950s, continuing through Blue Streak and Black Knight, to Black Arrow (which placed the UK's Prospero satellite in orbit in 1971). European launcher capability is now maintained in the European Space Agency's Ariane programme.

The Ferranti inertial platforms have always been at the heart of the Ariane guidance systems, and recently British Aerospace, using its experience with large carbon-fibre structures, has developed a facility – the SPELDA – which allows Ariane IV to carry two satellites in the same launch.

The USA has led the way in manned space activities based on a recoverable launch system – the Space Transportation System, commonly known as the Space Shuttle.

The STS is in fact a partially recoverable system in which the manned orbiter returns to Earth like a glider. It was developed by the USA as the next generation of launch vehicles, and it will be the main means of transportation for launching and maintaining the international Space Station planned by the US.

Europe made two contributions to the STS programme: the European Space Agency's development of Spacelab – a pressurised laboratory designed to fit into the Shuttle and accommodate astronauts in a 'shirt-sleeve environment'; and pallets developed by British Aerospace to fly on the Shuttle with experiments to be exposed to space conditions. The work on Spacelab is now being exploited in the form of ESA's Eureka – an experiment carrier designed to be launched by STS, left in orbit for several months, and then recovered.

ESA is currently examining a proposal to develop Hermes – a small manned space plane, intended to be launched on the next generation of Ariane launcher (Ariane V).

Black Arrow. Britain developed the Black Arrow launch vehicle in the late 1960s under the technical direction of Space Department, Royal Aircraft Establishment. When it put the technological satellite PROSPERO into orbit in October 1971, Britain became the fifth country in the world to launch its own satellite.

PROSPERO was designed to test a range of British electronic units and advanced satellite technologies in orbit. Its nominal lifetime was one year, but it is still operational, and most of its sub-systems are working satisfactorily.

A photograph of an Ariane III rocket in the middle of a launch. The rocket is white with a dark brown section near the top. It is ascending vertically, leaving a large, billowing white plume of exhaust and smoke behind it. The background is a clear blue sky with some light clouds. The rocket has several logos and text on it, including 'Ariane 10' and the ESA logo. The launch pad structure is visible at the bottom left.

Ariane III. The European Space Agency's Ariane launcher system became the first in the world to be operated on a commercial basis when it put a privately owned American satellite into orbit in May 1984. British firms provide much of the guidance system (including the inertial gyro package which ensures that the satellites are delivered into the correct orbit), the release system which holds the rocket on the launch pad until full thrust, and (in the case of Ariane IV) the SPELDA which allows two satellites to be carried in the same launch.

SPACE STATION AND COLUMBUS

Europe recognised mutual benefit in President Reagan's invitation to participate in the development of an international Space Station, and agreed to co-operate. The preparatory work has already begun, and Britain is heavily involved in this under ESA's Columbus programme.

Columbus covers the construction of three items of hardware:

- A pressurised module to be integrated with the Space Station as a laboratory for material and biological research in microgravity.
- A smaller version of the pressurised module, which, together with a resource module, will form a man-tended free-flier. In free-flying mode, this will provide a facility for conducting sensitive life-science and materials research, and very-low - microgravity experiments, away from the disturbances of the main station. It will be man-tended

periodically to service experiments needing human attention, and to change units, replace materials, collect results, and so on.

- A free-flying space platform or platforms, launched into polar orbit, and designed to be man-tended for maintenance, refuelling, exchange of units, and possibly the supply and collection of materials and products. It will be used primarily for earth observation.

In addition, ESA has offered to upgrade Eureka to serve as a smaller platform, co-orbiting with the main Station, principally for materials-processing and other scientific research.

Artist's impression of the Polar Platform.

The Platform is designed to be extendable. Initially it could have as many as four payload module berthing points, generate up to 5 kW electrical power, and incorporate a fully active cooling system, and a data communications link, via a data-relay satellite, operating at up to 300 MBPS. It would orbit at altitudes between 600 and 800 km.

Britain's main focus in the Columbus Programme is on the polar platforms. Reflecting this interest, British Aerospace, as the prime contractor, is leading an international team of sixteen companies in an extensive project-definition and design study.

Columbus envisages these platforms as permanent facilities, in low earth orbit, to which users will be able to attach payloads for as long, or as short, a period as required. Their first use is likely to be for the deployment of an extensive suite of

sensors and instruments for remote sensing of the Earth's surface and atmosphere, and possibly for stellar observations and astronomy.

Other UK companies, including Logica and Marconi, are involved in the preparatory programmes for the other parts of the Columbus programme.

In parallel with these studies, the BNSC is undertaking a major study to determine the potential users of the Space Station, with the long-term objective of establishing its scientific and commercial scope.

For example, the Space Station will offer opportunities for exploiting the potential of very-low-gravity and high-vacuum environments in work on alloys, semiconductors, optical materials and pharmaceuticals – or, indeed, on the physiology of man himself.

To explore this new area of R&D, the UK is taking a share in ESA's microgravity programme, and carrying out a wide range of studies on the possible benefits to ground-based industry.

Artist's impression of the International Space Station

GROUND EQUIPMENT AND SERVICES

British Telecom International's Teleport in London's Docklands was established to meet the rapidly growing demands of the City's businesses, and the increasing number of broadband cable television networks in the UK and the rest of Europe. Six terminals are planned, providing a full range of advanced communications services using digital transmission techniques and videoconferencing links.

Space activities are widely regarded as consisting only of satellites and space craft, and ground stations and equipment are frequently ignored. But the earth-bound infrastructure is, of course, just as important a part of space technology as the space-borne hardware. Investment in ground facilities is usually at least equal to that in the space segment!

British industry's contributions in this sector include:

- Large standard earth stations with 13-30 m diameter antennae for trunk telephony and TV distribution in the INTELSAT, EUTELSAT and INMARSAT systems – for example, those provided for the new British Telecom station in London's docklands.
- Smaller antennae, and a range of digital equipments, for business and other specialised satellite communications services.
- Ship- and airborne stabilised antennae and ship/earth stations for the INMARSAT services.
- Tracking, telemetry and command (TT&C) stations and satellite system-control centres.
- Transportable, vehicle-mounted, man-pack, shipborne and airborne terminals for the defence communications sector.
- Up-link feeder stations and receive-only terminals for cable television and outside broadcast services.
- Terminals for use with the navigation and search-and-rescue services of NAVSTAR-GPS and the SARSAT-COSPAS systems.
- Ground facilities for reception, archiving, processing and dissemination of meteorological and remote-sensing data, ranging from the computers and software controlling the satellite and its TT&C stations, to the weather forecasting facilities which merge the satellite data with terrestrial radar data and other conventional information.
- Geographical information systems incorporating satellite and terrestrial information sources.
- Part of the control-centre facilities for the Giotto (Halley's Comet) mission.
- The development of sophisticated support facilities for space research, including real-time remote control of microgravity experiments and the in-orbit refurbishment of satellites.

One of the ten dish aerals at Goonhilly Earth Station, Cornwall.

ORGANISATIONS PARTICIPATING IN BRITISH SPACE PROGRAMMES

The following tables list the scientific and commercial groups in the UK involved in space activity. Details of points of contact, addresses etc. can be found in a directory of British space activity available from the BNSC.

Government Laboratories and Establishments

British Antarctic Survey
British Museum (Natural History)
Meteorological Office
Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Natural Environment Research Council
National Physical Laboratory
National Remote Sensing Centre
NERC Unit for Thematic Information Services
Royal Airforce
Royal Aircraft Establishment
Royal Greenwich Observatory
Royal Navy
Royal Observatory
Royal Signal & Radar Establishment
Science and Engineering Research Council

United Kingdom Industrial Space Committee

British Aerospace Plc
DCC Limited
Ferranti PLC
Logica Space & Defence Systems Limited
Marconi Communications Systems Ltd.
Marconi Space Systems Ltd.
Racal-Decca Advanced Development Ltd.
Royal Ordnance Plc
SAC Technology Limited
Smith Associates Ltd.
Software Sciences Ltd.
Standard Telecommunications Laboratories Ltd.
Systems Designers Scientific
Thorn EMI Electronics Ltd.
Westland Plc

British Association of Remote Sensing Companies

British Aerospace Plc
Clyde Surveys Ltd.
ERSAC Ltd.
GEC Research Ltd.
GEMS of Cambridge Ltd.
General Technology Systems Ltd.
Geomorphological Services Ltd.
Geosurvey International Ltd.
Hays Space Technology
Hunting Geology and Geophysics Ltd.
Logica Space and Defence Systems Ltd.
Nigel Press Associates Ltd.
Oceanfix International Ltd.
Scott Wilson Kirkpatrick and Partners.
Smith Associates Ltd.
Spectrascan Ltd.

Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges

Principal UK Space Research Groups: Departments and Laboratories

Principal UK Remote Sensing Research Groups: Departments and Laboratories

Aberdeen University	—	Geography
Aberystwyth University	Physics	Geography
St. Andrews University	—	Geography
Aston University	Physics	Civil Engineering
Bangor University	—	Marine Science
Belfast University (Queen's)	Pure and Applied Physics	Geography
Birmingham University	Physics; Space Research	Electrical and Electronic Eng.; Geography
Bristol University	Physics	Geography
Cambridge University	—	Geography
Cardiff University	—	Civil Engineering
Central London Polytechnic	—	Civil Engineering
Coventry Polytechnic	—	Geography
Dundee University	—	Carnegie Laboratory of Physics
Durham University	—	Geography
East Anglia University	—	Environmental Sciences
Edinburgh University	—	Meteorology
Essex University	Physics	—
Glasgow University	—	Geography
Hatfield Polytechnic	—	Civil Engineering
Heriot-Watt University	Physics	—
Huddersfield Polytechnic	—	Geography
Hull University	Physics	—
Keele University	—	Geography
Kent University	The Electronics Laboratories	—
Kingston-upon-Thames Polytechnic	—	Geography and Computing
Lampeter College	—	Geography
Lancaster University	Environmental Sciences	Environmental Sciences
Leeds University	Physics	—
Leicester University	Astronomy; Physics	Geography
Liverpool University	—	Geography
London University:	—	—
— Birbeck College	—	Geography
— Imperial College	Physics	Blackett Laboratory
— Queen Mary College	Applied Mathematics; Physics	—
— Royal Holloway and Bedford New College	—	Geography
— School of Oriental and African Studies	—	Geography
— University College	Physics and Astronomy; Mullard Space Science Laboratory	Photogrammetry and Surveying
Luton College	—	Geography
Manchester University	Metallurgy; Nuffield Radio Astronomy Laboratories	Civil and Structural Engineering; Geography
Manchester University Institute of Science and Technology	Science and Technology	—
Newcastle-upon-Tyne University	Physics	Geography
North East London Polytechnic	—	Land Surveying
North London Polytechnic	—	Geography
Nottingham University	Civil Engineering	—
Open University	Earth Sciences	—
Oxford University	Clarendon Laboratory	—
Plymouth Polytechnic	—	Geographical Sciences
Portsmouth Polytechnic	—	Geography
Preston Polytechnic	—	Electrical and Electronic Engineering
Reading University	—	Geography; Meteorology
Salford University	—	Geography
Sheffield University	Computational Maths	Geography
Silsoe College	—	NRSC Regional Centre
Southampton University	Physics	Geography
Sunderland Polytechnic	—	Geography
Surrey University	Telecommunications Research Group	Civil Engineering
Sussex University	Astronomy Centre; Physics	—
Swansea University	—	Geography; Oceanography
York University	Physics	—

More information

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